

PLANET4B Impact assessment - BeSt Graz

Duration: approx. 1 hour

Informed Consent: go through the information and consent sheet, which should be sent to the interviewee in advance; clarify any open questions; obtain written consent => Start audio recording

Interview questions to women* of the GAIA garden LC

Intro – Process

1. What did you enjoy most in being part of the GAIA garden?
2. How regularly did you participate in the GAIA garden?
Did your engagement change over time? (Can you tell us more about the reasons behind that change?)
3. What made it challenging to participate in the GAIA garden? (Barriers from the project side, personal ones, etc.?)
4. In which respects did you perceive the garden as a co-creative effort?
What (skills and knowledge) could you contribute?
What did you learn from others?

Change attitude

5. How has being part of the gardening group influenced your perspective on gardening/
biodiversity/
food and
green spaces in urban settings?
6. What were key moments/eye-openers for you, where you gained new perspectives/
challenging your existing beliefs?
7. When a friend asks you what they can do to actively contribute to conserving biodiversity in their own lives, what would you recommend?
How do you see your own role in contributing to biodiversity conservation?

Change in behaviour

8. What personal changes have you noticed since joining the GAIA garden?
What in the garden specifically affected those changes?
How did your involvement in the GAIA garden impact your life and actions outside the group?
9. Which new insights influenced your behaviour regarding gardening/
biodiversity/
food and
green spaces in urban settings?
10. For which individuals is it easier to contribute to biodiversity conservation?
What makes it difficult (barriers) for you personally to contribute to biodiversity conservation?
What prevents you from acting on what you have learned in the GAIA garden?
11. What are your plans to support biodiversity conservation in the future?

12. What are your plans for future engagement in the GAIA garden and/or in other community activities?

Personal data¹

13. Intersectionality/Diversity item set – see Annex (DiMIS questionnaire)
14. How many people live with you in your household (How many adults, how many children <14yrs.?)
15. How many of the adults between 18 and 64 yrs. in your household – who are not in education or retired – have no employment (incl. self-employment)?
16. What is the netto income of your household per year (sum up for all persons in your household: netto income without taxes, social security per months * 12 – or 13/14, depending, including pensions, unemployment benefits etc.)?
17. If you have an unexpected expense that you did not plan for (e.g., a repair), up to what amount of money could you afford it?

Conclusion

18. What is your primary takeaway from participating in this project? (What have you told your family or friends about it?)
19. If we are planning another project like this one, what advice would you give us? (What can we improve? What should stay the same?)
20. Is there anything else, you want to tell us?

Thank you!

¹ Intersectionality measured with 1.) Diversity item set (Stadler, Gertraud & Chesaniuk, Marie & Haering, Stephanie & Roseman, Julia & Strassburger, Vera & Schraudner, Martina. (2022). Diversified Innovations in the Health Sciences - Proposal for a Diversity Minimal Item Set. 10.31234/osf.io/bjyms)
2.) Poverty or danger of exclusion (<https://www.statistik.at/statistiken/bevoelkerung-und-soziales/gender-statistiken/armuts-oder-ausgrenzungsgefaehrung>, <https://www.statistik.at/statistiken/bevoelkerung-und-soziales/einkommen-und-soziale-lage/haushaltseinkommen>, https://www.statistik.at/fileadmin/pages/338/EU-SILC_2014_Bericht.pdf)